

LINGUISTICS, ITS MODERN TYPES AND THEIR INTERPRETATION IN UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Abstract: The forms and tendencies of contemporary linguistics are discussed in this article along with a variety of remarks and viewpoints.

Key words: Philology, linguistics, profession, creativity, culture

The science of language is referred to as "linguistics" and is actively employed in many European countries, including English, French, German, Spanish, Russian, and others. Language, or lingua, is the root of this word. As a result, linguistics is the Uzbek phrase for linguistics, and the two terms have a synonymous relationship.

The study and analysis of communication methods, or language as a system, as a single entity—a singularly complex social phenomenon—is the focus of linguistics, sometimes known as the science of linguistics. It is seen in several forms during this procedure. This results from the social nature of language and the necessity of studying and verifying it from various angles. From a scientific standpoint, this is entirely true.

The following are some ways that linguistics shows up in the study of language, which is a very potent symbol of spirituality and national wealth:

1. Dynamic linguistics.
2. Static linguistics.
3. Synchronous linguistics.
4. Diachronic linguistics.
5. Intralinguistics.
6. Extralinguistics.
7. Paralinguistics.
8. Psycholinguistics.

9. Sociolinguistics.
10. Mathematical linguistics.
11. Computer linguistics.
12. Cognitive linguistics.
13. Pragma linguistics.
14. Linguoculturology.

1. Dynamic linguistics. Language in its actual existence, in the active completion of diverse tasks in the communication process, in "progress, " and in change is the focus of dynamic linguistics.

2. Static linguistics. A particular time (portion) of perfectly synchronized language activity is identified and described by static linguistics. The condition of a particular "hard" element of the language associated to the present-modern era is examined by this discipline of linguistics, which, in contrast to dynamic linguistics, is entirely detached from and does not approach the process of language growth and change.

3. Synchronous linguistics. Static and structural linguistics are closely related to synchronous linguistics, which describes the "fixed, " "stagnant" condition of language during a specific time.

4. Diachronic linguistics. Diachronic linguistics, which studies the rules and outcomes of language development as well as the evolution of language units, is closely related to dynamic and atomic linguistics.

5. Intra linguistics (linguistics within oneself). Regardless of extra linguistic variables, internal linguistics examines the systematic relationships between language components. Phonology, lexicology, and grammar serve as the foundation for domestic linguistics study.

6. Extra linguistics. The study of external linguistics examines how language evolved and functions in relation to sociopolitical, sociohistorical, ethnic, and geographic circumstances. Thus, this branch of linguistics studies language as a social construct.

7. Paralinguistic. Directly related to speech activity, paralinguistic is the study of various aspects of speech, including speech pitch, expressive-emotional coloring, and hand and facial movements (gestures, facial expressions) that happen concurrently with the expression of thoughts during the speech process and are a constant companion of colloquial speech.

8. Psycholinguistics. As a blend of linguistics and psychology, psycholinguistics examines the speech process in terms of its correspondence, communicative relevance, content, and direction toward a particular socio-practical objective. He focuses particularly on the coherence of speech's form and content—the way ideas are expressed.

The formation and reception of speech units are particularly examined in psycholinguistics in light of linguistic possibilities, mental states during the speech process (change in thought-expression and understanding), the conditions (situation), sensitivity, similarity (analogy), differentiation (difference), and the mental states of the speaker and listener.

9. Sociolinguistics. The need and logical link between sociology and linguistics gives rise to sociolinguistics, which addresses the problem of the interaction between language and society. According to his interpretation, language is a social construct. The study of language—its character as a social phenomenon, its place and significance in society—is, in this sense, the most significant and fundamental subject in sociolinguistics.

The focus of sociolinguistics is the relationship between language and social interactions, social life, developmental phenomena, facts, and the causes of this relationship. This discipline specifically examines the processes, occurrences, and transformations brought about by the impact of social life in language—that is, extra linguistic, external factors—on the survival and advancement of society. Sociolinguistics, then, is the study of how social variables influences language, how they are reflected, and how they appear in the language system (structure).

It should be remembered that sociolinguistics uses statistical data, population census data, and questionnaire data methods to broaden its scope⁷.

10. Mathematical linguistics. The field of mathematical linguistics studies the potential applications of mathematical techniques (such as information theory, statistical approaches, etc.) to the study and description of language.

11. Computers linguistics. The primary objective of computer linguistics, a subfield of applied linguistics, is to use a computer to solve linguistics-related issues under its "guidance." More specifically, computational linguistics actively supports several activities, including statistical research, text editing, language translation, evaluation of subject-specific knowledge, and language instruction (learning).

12. Cognitive linguistics. One of the most recent developments in linguistics is cognitive linguistics. The need to collaborate between linguistics and cognitive science—the study of human knowledge—led to the development of this branch of linguistics.

13. Linguistic pragmatics. Based on the accomplishments and outcomes of structural linguistics, pragmatic linguistics is the outcome of cognitive (empirical) study at a new level. He uses the scenario of using a speech exercise as a linguistic unit as a system. As a result, it investigates and studies a particular speech activity, realization, and manifestation unit in conjunction with a variety of non-linguistic elements and at various levels, in connection to them.

14. Language and Culture. Psycholinguistics, ethnography, cultural studies, and linguistics served as the foundation for linguoculturalogy. He studies the relationship and influence of culture, ethnicity, and national mentality based on the principles of the anthropocentric paradigm⁸.

Thus, the science of linguistics, as a whole, as it was noted, studies the language system through its various peculiarities and spheres, with its entire essence, complexity, and unlimited communicative possibilities. In this process, he interacts with a number of disciplines, works in cooperation, actively participates in the

⁷ В.А.Аврорин. Проблемы изучения функциональной стороны языка (к Вопросу о предмете социолингвистики). -Л., 1975, стр: 242-245.

⁸ Shaykhislamov, N. (2020). In the Field of Modern Linguistics, Linguoculturalogy. *Мировая наука*, (8), 33-36.

coverage of such topical and extremely complex issues as language and society, language and history, language and development, language and thinking, language and speech.

The science of linguistics serves to confirm and prove that one of the most important, fundamental, unparalleled criteria for the development and prosperity of society is language - a means of communication. Additionally, it provides a strong basis for the development of national consciousness, national worldview, national pride, and national ideology by demonstrating to the learner the potential of the native language—the fact that there are hundreds of ways to express the same idea, thing, or event—developing creative thinking, thinking in the native language, and the distinctiveness of the native language's construction, which distinguishes it from other languages fundamentally. Additionally, it reflects the world "in its own way."

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